

Property of cadmium and zinc complex with *meso*-tetra(3,5-dibromo-4-hydroxyphenyl)porphyrin and simultaneous determination of cadmium and zinc by spectral correction method

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The reactions between cadmium(II) and *meso*-tetra(3,5-dibromo-4-hydroxyphenyl)porphyrin (TDBHPP) and zinc(II) and TDBHPP are both highly sensitive at pH 10. The β -correction technique has been applied in the simultaneous determination of Cd and Zn instead of the classical spectrophotometry. Two synthetic samples have been determined satisfactorily. Complex properties studies comprise the complex ratio, stepwise absorptivity and stability constant. In the presence of fluoride and sulphurea, the reaction is selective. The complexes are Cd(TDBHPP) and Zn(TDBHPP), having stability constants 3.67×10^6 and 1.13×10^6 , real absorptivity 2.25×10^5 at 445 nm and $2.24 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 435 nm, respectively, and the relative standard deviation is 2.3% for the determination of Cd and 2.2% for that of Zn in synthetic samples.

2-(5-Bromo-2-pyridylazo)-5-diethylaminophenol¹, 8-(*m*-hydroxyphenylazo)-7-hydro-4-methylcoumarin² and di-2-pyridylmethanone-2-(5-nitropyridyl)hydrazone³ are used in the determination of trace amounts of cadmium or zinc by spectrophotometry. The synthesis of the chromogenic reagent, *meso*-tetra(3,5-dibromo-4-hydroxyphenyl)porphyrin (TDBHPP) was reported earlier⁴.

TDBHPP

This reagent has been applied in the determination of single component such as lead⁵ and zinc⁶. In the present work, it was observed that the reaction solutions between TDBHPP and Cd^{II}, TDBHPP and Zn^{II} give different sensitive absorption wavelengths at pH 10. The maximal absorption of the ligand TDBHPP was located at about 430 nm, that of Cd-TDBHPP complex at 445 nm and of Zn-TDBHPP complex at 435 nm. Because of close proximity of the above three wavelengths, the use of ordinary spectrophotometry is limited in this study. The new technique, beta-correction spectrophotometry may eliminate the absorption effect of excess

of ligand to give out the real absorbance of the complex produced, and it has been applied⁷⁻⁹ for the determination of trace metals and analysis of many complex solutions. In the present work, it was applied in the simultaneous determination of trace amounts of Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} in synthetic sample and wastewater. By means of this principle not only were trace amounts of cadmium and zinc determined but also the properties of Cd-TDBHPP and Zn-TDBHPP complexes were evaluated easily. In this aspect, this method is more acceptable in principle and simpler in operation than the classical methods, for example, the molar ratio¹⁰, the continuous variation¹¹ and the equilibrium movement¹². In the determination of trace amounts of cadmium and zinc in water, the reagents, fluoride and sulphurea solution were able to mask the other metal ions.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra : Fig. 1 shows the absorption spectra of TDBHPP, Cd-TDBHPP and Zn-TDBHPP solutions. From curves 1, 4 and 5, the peak absorption of TDBHPP was located at 430 nm, that of Zn-TDBHPP complex at 435 nm and Cd-TDBHPP complex at 445 nm. However, from curves 2 and 3, the valley absorption was not located at 430 nm but at 480 nm. Therefore, the three wavelengths, 435 (Zn complex peak), 445 (Cd complex peak) and 480 nm (complex valley absorption) are selected as the wavelengths so as to obtain the highest sensitivity. From curve 1, $\beta_{435/480} = 3.19$ and $\beta_{435/480} = 2.66$; $\alpha_{480/435}^{\text{Zn}} = 0.032$ from curve 4, $\alpha_{480/445}^{\text{Cd}} = 0.129$ from curve 5. Therefore, the expressions developed were : $A_c = 1.11 (\Delta A - 3.19 \Delta A')$ for cal-

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of TDBHPP, Cd-TDBHPP and Zn-TDBHPP complex solutions at pH 10 : (1) 0.40 μmol TDBHPP, (2) Zn (10 μg)-TDBHPP (0.30 μmol) reaction solution, (3) Cd(20 μg)-TDBHPP (0.30 μmol) reaction solution, (4) Zn(200 μg)-TDBHPP (0.10 μmol) complex solution (no free TDBHPP), (5) Cd(50 μg)-TDBHPP (0.10 μmol) reaction solution (no free TDBHPP). All (1), (4) and (5) against water reference and the others against reagent blank reference.

culuation of the real absorption of Zn-TDBHPP complex at 435 nm and $A_c = 1.52 (\Delta A - 2.66 \Delta A')$ for calculation of the real absorption of Zn-TDBHPP complex at 445 nm. In fact, the spectral correction technique is one of the dual-wavelength spectrophotometric methods too, but it is different from those of other¹³ in principle.

Effect of addition of TDBHPP solution : Fig. 2 shows the effect of the addition of TDBHPP solution on the absorption of BDNPF and its Cd and Zn complex solutions. From curves 1 and 2, it is difficult to calculate accurately the complex ratios of Cd or Zn to TDBHPP with the molar ratio method because the inflexion points are not clear. From

Fig. 2. Effect of the addition of TDBHPP solution on absorbances of Cd(20 μg)-TDBHPP and Zn(10 μg)-TDBHPP reaction solutions at pH 10 : (1) Zn-TDBHPP solution at 435 nm, (2) Cd-TDBHPP solution at 445 nm, (3-1) same as (1) and (3-2) same as (2) but both at 480 nm.

them, the absorption of Cd-TDBHPP and Zn-TDBHPP reaction solutions both reached peak maximum when the addition of 1.00 mmol dm^{-3} TDBHPP was 0.30 ml. Therefore, 0.30 ml of TDBHPP solution was added in the determination of Cd and Zn. The effective fraction (η) of the ligand TDBHPP and the complex ratio (γ) of TDBHPP to Zn or Cd were calculated according to the expressions⁷.

$$\gamma' = \eta \times \frac{C_L}{C_M} \quad \text{where, } \eta = \frac{\alpha \Delta A - \Delta A'}{(1 - \alpha \beta) A'_0}$$

The terms, C_M and C_L indicate the concentrations (mol dm^{-3}) of Cd or Zn and TDBHPP in the beginning, respectively, A'_0 is the absorbance of the blank reagent. Their curves are shown in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively. From curves in Fig. 4, both γ approached to the maximum 1 when the addition of TDBHPP solution was over 0.25 ml. Therefore,

Fig. 3. Effect of the addition of TDBHPP solution on η : (1) Zn(10 μg)-TDBHPP solution and (2) Cd(20 μg)-TDBHPP solution.

Fig. 4. Effect of the addition of TDBHPP solution on γ : (1) Zn(10 μg)-TDBHPP solution and (2) Cd(20 μg)-TDBHPP solution.

the complexes Cd(TDBHPP) and Zn(TDBHPP) were formed at pH 10. From Fig. 3, the effective fraction of BDNPF is 73.3% in Cd-TDBHPP solution and 51.5% in Zn-TDBHPP solution, respectively, when 0.3 ml of TDBHPP solution was added. Therefore, over 25% TDBHPP is free. It is irrefutable for the excess of TDBHPP

to affect the absorption measurement of complex.

Effect of pH : The effect of variation of pH of the solution on absorption of the reaction solution is shown in Fig. 5. The absorption of Cd-TDBHPP reached high value at pH 9.8–11 (curve 1) and that of Zn-TDBHPP at 9.5–10.6 (curve 2). Therefore, pH 10 was selected in this study.

Fig. 5. Effect of pH on absorption of Cd(20 µg)-TDBHPP and Zn(10 µg)-TDBHPP reaction solutions at pH 10 : (1) Cd-TDBHPP solution at 445 nm and (2) Zn-TDBHPP solution at 435 nm.

Effect of time : Fig. 6 shows the effect of the reaction time on absorption of Cd-TDBHPP solution at 445 nm and that of Zn-TDBHPP solution at 435 nm. Both the reactions were rapid and after 5 min, the reactions were complete. However, beyond 20 min, the absorption of the complex was reduced. Therefore, the absorption measurement of the reaction solution was carried out between 5 and 20 min.

Fig. 6. Effect of the reaction time on absorption of Cd(20µg)-TDBHPP and Zn(10 µg)-TDBHPP reaction solutions at pH 10 : (1) Cd-TDBHPP solution at 445 nm and (2) Zn-TDBHPP solution at 435 nm.

Determination of real absorptivity and stability constant : The stepwise stability constant (K_n), cumulative constant (K) and stepwise absorptivity (ϵ) of the complex can be calculated from the equations⁹,

$$K_n = \frac{\gamma' + 1 - n}{(n - \gamma')(C_L - \gamma' C_M)}$$

$$K = \prod_{n=1}^{\gamma} K_n$$

$$\epsilon_{ML_n}^{\lambda_2} = \frac{A_c}{\delta C_M (\gamma' + 1 - n)} - \frac{n - \gamma'}{(\gamma' + 1 - n)} \epsilon_{ML_{n-1}}^{\lambda_2}$$

The term n indicates the n -th complex and δ the thickness of cell. The complex ratio γ' must be between $(n-1)$ and n by preparing the mixed solution. The following solutions were prepared for the determination of stepwise real absorptivity and stability constant of the complexes : 10.0 µg Cd^{II} with 0.150 µmol TDBHPP and 10.0 µg Zn^{II} with 0.100 µmol TDBHPP in 25 ml of solution. Four replicate determinations of each solution were carried out. The real absorptivity of Zn-TDBHPP and Cd-TDBHPP complex was calculated as 2.24×10^5 at 435 nm and 2.25×10^5 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 445 nm, respectively. Their stability constants were 1.13×10^6 and 3.67×10^6 , respectively, both in ionic strength 0.025 M and room temperature (15°).

Calibration graph : A series of standard Cd (0–25.0 µg/25ml) and Zn (0–12.0 µg/25ml) solutions were prepared and their absorption measured. The beta-correction absorbance, A_β was computed and the standard curves are shown in Fig. 7. From curves 1– x and 2– x , the beta-correction absorption of the Cd or Zn reaction solution with TDBHPP is found linear between 0 and 12.0 µg Zn and 0 and 25.0 µg Cd. The following equations are expressed : $A_{\beta 1Cd} = 0.0282x_{Cd}$ at 435 nm, $A_{\beta 2Cd} = 0.0389x_{Cd}$ at 445 nm for Cd-TDBHPP solution and $A_{\beta 1Zn} = 0.108x_{Zn}$ at 435 nm, $A_{\beta 2Zn} = 0.0819x_{Zn}$ at 445 nm for Zn-TDBHPP solution.

Fig. 7. Standard curve for the determination of Cd^I and Zn^{II} at pH 10 : (1) A_β of Cd-TDBHPP solution at 435 nm, (2) A_β of Cd-TDBHPP solution at 445 nm, (3) A_β of Zn-TDBHPP solution at 435 nm and (4) A_β of Zn-TDBHPP solution at 445 nm.

Therefore, $a_{1Cd} = 0.0352$, $a_{2Cd} = 0.0427$, $a_{1Zn} = 0.0449$ and $a_{2Zn} = 0.0107$. The following matrix was established and used for the simultaneous determination of Cd between 0 and 25.0 $\mu\text{g}/25\text{ml}$ and Zn between 0 and 12.0 $\mu\text{g}/25\text{ml}$:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0.108 & 0.0282 \\ 0.0819 & 0.0389 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_{Zn} \\ x_{Cd} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \Delta A - 3.19 \Delta A' \\ \Delta A - 2.66 \Delta A' \end{pmatrix}$$

Precision and detection limit : Seven replicate determinations of standard solution containing simultaneously 5.00 μg Cd and 5.00 μg Zn were carried out. The average of Cd and Zn was equal to 4.78 and 4.73 μg , respectively, the relative standard deviations (RSDs) being 6.9 and 3.9%. We used 0.010 of the real absorbance of the complex to calculate the detection limit of Cd and Zn as follows : 0.2 μg Cd and 0.1 μg Zn/25 ml.

Effect of foreign ions : Once the masking reagent was added, none of the following ions affected the simultaneous determination of 5 μg of Cd and 5 μg of Zn (<20% error) : 1 mg of Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , SO_3^{2-} , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$, NO_3^- , NH_4^+ , K^+ , Na^+ ; 200 μg of Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} , Al^{III} , Sn^{II} , Ge^{IV} , Sb^{III} , Ti^{IV} , Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} , V^V , PO_4^{3-} ; 20 μg of Pb^{II} , Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Hg^{II} .

Cd and Zn were simultaneously determined in synthetic sample and wastewater. The recovery of standard cadmium and zinc was 90.9–105% and 90.5–102.5%, respectively, and their RSDs in synthetic sample being 2.3 and 2.2%.

Experimental

Absorption spectra were recorded with a Shimadzu UV-VIS 265 spectrophotometer in 10 mm glass cell. A PHS-2c (Leici Instruments, Shanghai) acidometer was used to adjust the acidity of the complex solution and samples.

Standard Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} solutions (1000 mg dm^{-3}) were prepared from the metals (purity >99.9%, Shanghai Reagents) by dissolving in HCl and diluted; standard work solutions (2.00 mg dm^{-3}) were prepared daily by dilution. Standard TDBHPP solution (1.00 mmol dm^{-3}) of *meso*-tetra(3,5-dibromo-4-hydroxyphenyl)porphyrin (TDBHPP, >98%; Changke Reagents Institute, Shanghai) was prepared in DMF (A.R., Shanghai Chemicals) and stored in a dark bottle. The buffer solution of pH 10 was prepared by mixing borate and NaOH solution, to adjust the acidity of the reaction. Masking reagent was prepared by mixing 5% sodium fluoride (A.R., Shanghai Chemicals; 100 ml) and 2% sulfourea (A.R., Shanghai Chemicals; 100 ml).

Procedures

Determination of properties of complex : To 10.0 μg standard Zn^{II} or 20.0 μg standard Cd^{II} were added the buffer solution (2.5 ml) and standard TDBHPP solution, then di-

luted to 25 ml. After 5 min, its absorbance was measured at 435 (Zn solution) or 445 (Cd solution) and 480 nm, respectively. The real absorbance (A_c) of the complex was calculated according to the equation⁷,

$$A_c = \frac{\Delta A - \beta \Delta A'}{1 - \alpha \beta} \quad \text{where, } \alpha = \frac{\epsilon_{ML\lambda}^{\lambda 1}}{\epsilon_{ML\gamma}^{\lambda 2}} \quad \text{and } \beta = \frac{\epsilon_L^{\lambda 2}}{\epsilon_L^{\lambda 1}}$$

The terms ΔA and $\Delta A'$ are the absorbances of the reaction solution at 435 (Zn solution) or 445 (Cd solution) and 480 nm, against reagent blank reference, respectively. The coefficients α and β are named correction factors. The terms $\epsilon_{ML\gamma}^{\lambda 1}$, $\epsilon_{ML\gamma}^{\lambda 2}$, $\epsilon_L^{\lambda 1}$ and $\epsilon_L^{\lambda 2}$ indicate the molar absorptivity of complex ML_γ and ligand L at 435 (Zn solution) or 445 (Cd solution) and 480 nm, respectively.

Determination of Cd and Zn in sample : To a mixture of the buffer solution (pH 10; 2.5 ml), masking solution (1.0 ml) and TDBHPP solution (2.5 ml), was added a known volume of a sample solution containing less than 25.0 μg of Cd and 12.0 mg of Zn and then diluted to 25 ml. After 5 min, its absorbance was measured at 435, 445 and 480 nm against a reagent blank.

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